

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

SECURITIES IN ISLAMIC FINANCE, SUKUK WORLD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789229>

Abstract

The purpose of this article is to determine the importance of sukuk operations in the financing of large government projects as a result of the expansion of the sukuk market, which is one of the most important forms of Islamic finance. One of the most important forms of Islamic finance is debt securities, which have been proven to be interest-free bonds, ie sukuk, "equity certificates representing joint ownership of assets in a portfolio of fixed assets." Given the current economic situation and the crisis, it was found that the possibility of investing in a new class of assets is interpreted as a way to use capital more efficiently and effectively. A comparative overview of the neighboring Turkish market showed that the success of the Islamic banking system in sukuk operations in Kazakhstan has increased. It was noted that the introduction of sukuk in the Kazakhstan market has brought many prospects.

Keywords: sukuk, bonds, securities, Islamic banking, assets.

Introduction

When considering the main sources of Islamic finance, it is accepted that Islamic finance takes the Holy Qur'an as its main source, and then consists of financial activities carried out within the framework of Islamic principles, especially in the stages of application. In this context, this market was created by purchasing existing investment instruments that conform to Islamic principles or developing new investment instruments that conform to Islamic principles. The main elements prohibited by Islamic rules are transactions and payment of interest, engaging in illegal activities such as gambling, and activities related to uncertainty.

Today, Islamic finance with the advent of Islamic banking, which provides interest-free products and services, and over time, mudaraba (labor capital partnership), Musharaka (profit-loss partnership), Murabaha (cost plus margin sales), insurance and Ijara in the capital market (rent) many other financial products in accordance with Sharia rules financing, Takaful (Insurance), exception (purchase based on order). In principle, the Islamic mutual fund market is a very dynamic and open market. Islamic Investment Fund, in other words, Islamic securitization, sukuk; this means that Islamic value papers are issued to finance projects, including the development of infrastructure, the improvement of production, etc. [13. 283]

In this context, the purpose of issuing a Sukuk is to start a new project, develop an existing project, or use the funds raised to finance commercial activities according to the share due to the funds raised. In the sukuk system, the income received by the investor or sukuk holder; comes from the right to receive income from business activities, ownership of a certain asset, or a joint venture. Sukuk investors are not paid interest; specific economic transactions based on sharing or leasing assets are distributed. When the reasons for the release of sukuk are considered from the point of view of issuers; Although financing is the expansion and diversification of the investor base, from the point of

view of investors; the possibility of investing in a new asset class can be interpreted as a way to use capital more efficiently and effectively, and it can be explained from the point of view of the possibility of applying it to some government projects in Turkey and Kazakhstan.

The main part

DEFINITION AND TYPES OF SUKUK

Definition and content of sukuk

Sukuk are long-term and short-term securities (also called "Islamic bonds") issued under Sharia law, covered by tangible assets. Sukuk papers allow Muslims to invest funds for profit purposes without contradicting Islamic law, which does not allow them to receive trade interest (RIBA). It attracts the funds of Islamic investors who cannot invest in simply borrowed financial instruments related to religious faith. [8.66] the issuers of sukuk are Islamic and non-Islamic organizations. Sukuk is Arabic. "Sakk" — "legal document, act, receipt" is an incorrect concept that is considered a "Sukuk Islamic bond". Sukuk AAOIFI (accounting and audit organization for Islamic financial institutions) "Co-named securities representing private property interests in existing or future asset portfolios. Here, debt-based sukuk agreements also differ from ordinary bonds. Simple bond: imposing a net debt burden on the Issuer. The creditor, the borrower is the ratio of money to money. Sukuk certificate: share of ownership in an actual or planned asset. The relationship between the issuer and the investor is based on a clear understanding in the business in question. The debt issued under sukuk is not charged with adding any surcharges for money. Only from the profits from the project, the partners will be able to separate the corresponding trophies from each other. In Arabic, the word Senet is used for bills and bonds, while for Islamic bonds, the word "sukuk", which is the plural form of the word saqq, is used. [3. 315-329]

Accounting and audit institution of Islamic financial institutions (AAOIFI) .

Sukuk, representing the same values after issue; the amounts from issue are invested as planned; certificates representing rights and shares in fixed assets, depending on the type of investment made, or granting partnership rights to a project or special investment activity.

In principle, sukuk indicates the right to own or profit from an asset. The right and claim in sukuk is not only the right of money circulation, but also the right of property.

According to the Islamic Academy of fiqh, the concept of sukuk is mainly related to two rules. The rules under consideration can be represented as follows.

Property owned by any individual can be represented by written bonds and documents.

These bonds and documents can be sold at market prices.

In the basic sense, we can summarize the features of sukuk as follows;

- This is the plural of SACC and they are equally valuable testimonies. They represent property rights with Indivisible shares.

- They are also called interest-free bonds on the market.

- Ensures the establishment of rights in favor of certificate holders for special projects or assets subject to special investment.

- They are asset-based ("asset-based", "asset-backed")

- As a rule, the underlying assets are transferred to a special purpose company (APL/SPV). - They establish the right to income from assets.

- Since it is possible to quote in organized markets, the rating organizations can be evaluated.

- They can be sold in the secondary market.

- They can be fixed or variable income.

Sukuk provides its investor with a basis for financing in exchange for interest income on traditional bonds.

It provides a share of profit from the income received from the asset it owns, which differs from traditional bonds in this respect [5. 33]. This feature distinguishes sukuk from traditional bonds. While traditional bonds consist of interest-bearing securities, sukuk are essentially investment certificates consisting of ownership in the asset basket [14. 78-100]. In this context, the main differences between bonds and sukuk are as shown in Table 1.

Differences between sukuk and traditional bonds

	bonds	sukuk
Credit risk	Issuer risk	Issuer risk
Terms and conditions	Using the standard bond	Like Bond
Pricing	Depending on the credit rating and demand	Conditional bonds are taken as indicators
Interest payment	Regular coupon payment	Regular payment, such as coupon payment
Credit rating	Like the credit profile of the debtor company	Like the credit profile of the debtor company
Investor profile	Ordinary investor	Although there are Islamic investors in general, this profile changes over time.
Hedge	GDI / interest rate swaps	There is no tool for direct hedge sukuk.
Maturity	Can be short, medium and long-term	It is medium-term, usually 3-5 years, and its payback period is slowly extended.

The purpose of the issue of sukuk is to conclude a new transaction based on the funds raised and the share in the possession. Starting a project, developing an existing project, or using the funds raised for commercial purposes to finance an action. In the sukuk system, the income received by the investor or sukuk holder; the right to receive income from business activities, a particular asset, property or joint venture arises from his possession. On the other hand, the sukuk technique also differs from other securities that can be called in the form of an asset certificate or securitized asset (securitized assets) it must be based on being [15. 2009:13]. Understanding the sukuk system first of all, it is necessary to know the asset-backed securities (ADMK) system. A company that has a portfolio of receivables in the VDMC system, sells the portfolio to a Special Purpose Vehicle (Special Purpose Vehicle/SPV) and SPV turns a portfolio into securities. At the same time, investment banks mediate the sale of assets to investors. In the sukuk system, material, real business relations (for example, profit and loss, partnership) or accounts receivable arising from a financial lease agreement. Because sukuk is carried out on the basis of

securitization, can also be classified as Secured Bonds [15. 2009:14]. As the most crucial difference between sukuk and bonds; an asset - based sukuk certificate whereas a bond is a certificate based on the amount of money borrowed.

This also means that although bonds have a certain amount of income guarantee, sukuk does not have such a guarantee. However, in addition to ownership in sukuk, other guarantees may be granted.

The purpose of issuing a Sukuk is to start a new project, develop an existing project, or use the funds raised to finance commercial activities in accordance with the share due to the funds raised. In the sukuk system, the income that an investor or sukuk holder receives; on the other hand, sukuk is derived from other securities that can technically be referred to as asset securities or securitized assets, otherwise it must be based on existence [15. 2009:13]. To understand the sukuk system, you first need to know the asset-backed securities (VDMK) system. A company with a portfolio of receivables in the VDMK system sells this portfolio to a Special Purpose Vehicle (special Purpose Vehi-

cle/SPV), and the SPV exchanges the portfolio for securities. At the same time, investment banks mediate the sale of these securities to investors. Since the sukuk system has asset-based securitization of receivables arising from specific commercial relationships (e.g. profit sharing) or financial leasing contracts, sukuk is backed by asset bonds [15. 2009: 14]. As the most crucial difference between a Sukuk and a bond; a Sukuk is

an asset - based certificate, while a bond is a certificate based on borrowed money. In addition, while the bonds have a certain income guarantee, sukuk does not have such a guarantee. However, other guarantees may be provided in addition to ownership in sukuk. Sukuk types defined by AAOIFI [6. 8]

Sukuk species are defined by AAOIFI

1	Sukuk Al-Ijara	8	Sukuk Al-Murabaha
2	Sukukuzharah mousubuthuma	9	Sukuk Al-Musharaka
3	Sukukmanfajarah	10	Sukuk Al-mudaraba
4	Sukukmanfajarah mousubuthuma	11	Sukuk Al-waqala
5	Sukkimilkijat Al-khadamat	12	Sukuk Al-muzraa
6	Sukuk Al-istisna	13	Sukuk Al-moussaka
7	Sukuk al-Salam	14	Sukuk Al-muqarasa

As can be seen from this table, there are many types of sukuk defined by the organization for accounting and supervision of Islamic financial institutions. The study discusses leasing indexed sukuk (Ijara sukuk), venture capital indexed sukuk (mudaraba

sukuk), profit and loss partnership investment indexed sukuk (Musharaka sukuk), forward supply contract indexed sukuk (hi sukuk), general purpose financial support Sukuk (types such as sukuk), Special Infrastructure Financing indexed Sukuk (Istisna Sukuk).

Figure 1: main types of Sukuk

Indexed by rent sukuk: Izhara sukuk.

The word Ijara means "allow". As a term, it refers to Financial Leasing, which is used by interest-free banks and is similar to conventional banks. In this type of sukuk, interest-free banks, equipment, buildings, etc.he buys things and rents them out to his customers in exchange for a fixed rental income [11. 129].

In Ijara sukuk, one of the parties buys the equipment that the customer wants to use by paying a rental fee and leases it to the customer for a rental fee,

Securitized asset under Islamic financing; Sukuk world and Turkish market overview

The lease term and fee are set in advance, and the ownership of the property that is the subject of the contract remains with the lessor. This type of sukuk offers the owner an equal partnership or ownership of the leased property under the usufruct of the property. Ijara sukuk gives its owners the right to own the property, receive the rent and dispose of the sukuk in such a way

that it does not affect the rights of the tenant, for example, to buy and sell. Izhara sukuk holders bear the costs of maintaining said property [15. 2009:19].

- way to work;
- The debtor sells the asset in question to the SPV at a pre-agreed price.
- By issuing the same sukuk certificates at the price purchased by the SPV provides financing.
- The lease agreement stipulates that the presence of an obligation is the lessee for a certain period of time. It is signed between the SPV and the debtor with re-leasing.
- The SPV periodically receives rent from the borrower.
- The rent is distributed to investors (sukuk holders).
- At maturity or in case of fragmentation, the SPV will be at a predetermined price

returns the asset to the debtor. This amount must be equal to all debts on the terms of icara sukuk.

Venture capital indexed sukuk: mudaraba sukuk.

Mudaraba is the provision of equity through management support for all types of enterprises within the framework of a profit and loss partnership, and in this regard, it attracts a structure similar to venture capital. In mudaraba sukuk, the issuer of the certificate is mudarib (entrepreneur). Financiers are owners of capital, and the funds raised are mudaraba capital. Certificate holders are the owners of assets in the Mudaraba business and a share of the profit from the transaction. Certificate holders also bear the costs if they occur. Mudaraba sukuk represents joint ownership and grants the sukuk buyer the right to participate in individual projects against the sukuk issuer. The mudaraba sukuk treaty is based on the official notification at the time of the issuance, which contains all the information indicating the type of capital, the rate of return and other conditions in accordance with the rules of Sharia [15. 2009: 18].

way to work;

- Mudarib agrees with the project owner for the launch/construction of the project.

come on.

- SPV issues sukuk to raise funds.

- Mudarib receives final capital receipts and a fixed return payment from the project activities.

- Mudarib will deliver to the owner after the project is completed.

Sukuk indexed in the investment of a profit and loss partnership. Musharaka sukuk

Musharaka is a partnership of Labor and capital. It is possible to have a partner with a different or the same amount of capital participation. Each partner has the right to use capital within established limits. Commercial activities may be limited to only one area, or they may be designated as applicable in many areas if an agreement is reached. Although the distribution of losses is distributed at the rate of participation in capital, according to the agreement, the distribution of profits can be different. [17. 129]. In Musharaka sukuk, the issuing party is the party that invokes a special finance company (SPV) created to carry out a specific project or activity. The funders are partners of the Musharaka treaty. The funds raised as shares represent the contribution of the participants to the capital of Musharaka. Sukuk holders also own the assets of the company and are entitled to the profits that are carried out. The main difference between Musharaka and mudaraba is that the capital comes from both sides [15. 2009: 18].

way to work;

- The company (as Musharaka) contributes to the soil or other physical assets that are the target of Musharaka.

- SPV (as Musharik) gives cash (emission income of investors in Musharak, etc.).

- Musharaka appoints an agent authorized by the company to develop land or physical valuables and sell/lease valuables developed on behalf of Musharaka, with the addition of additional cash to Musharaka.

- The Authorized Agent (company) receives a stimulating variable remuneration in addition to the regular agency fee.

- The profit is distributed to sukuk shareholders.

-The company provides a non-refundable guarantee for the purchase of Musharaka SPV shares on a semi-annual basis at a pre-agreed price, and at the end of the specified period, the SPV will not have a Musharaka share.

Sukuk indexed to forward delivery contract: Salem sukuk

Salem – a contract of sale, which is carried out when the seller undertakes to transfer the goods to the buyer at a later date [18. 128]. Salem sukuk-documents issued as equivalent to the collection of Salem capital. Buyers of documents exported with this accumulated capital acquire ownership of the goods sold on the basis of Salem. The issuer of documents is the seller of these goods. Members are buyers of goods. Membership fees to be paid are the cost of purchasing goods. Those who issue Salem documents are the owners, and these owners have the right to sell Salem-based goods with issued Salem sukuk documents [8. 66].

way to work;

- VKSH signs an agreement with the debtor to find both goods and buyers.

The obligator undertakes to buy the goods on behalf of the sukuk-buyers and then sell the goods for profit on behalf of the sukuk owners.

- Hello documents are issued to investors and VKSH sukuk receives a refund. - Salem returns are given to the debtor, who sells the goods later. - VKSH receives the goods from the debtor.

"They sell the goods for profit on behalf of the mandatory sukuk holders.

- Sukuk holders receive income from the sale of goods [7. 24].

Sukuk indexed to support general purpose funding: Murabaha sukuk

Murabaha is defined as a sales transaction made by adding the amount of agreed profit to the value of the goods [11. 26]. Murabaha sukuk is the certificate giver, the seller of the goods, the buyer of the goods who receives the Murabaha, and the fund is the cost of purchasing the goods. Certificate holders own Murabaha merchandise and are entitled to the final selling price when reselling the merchandise [15. 21].

way to work;

- The main contract is concluded between the SPV and the borrower.

- SPV issues sukuk to investors and receives sukuk returns.

- SPV immediately buys the goods from the seller.

- Add the profit margin of the SPV product within the agreed period from the spot price sells to the debtor for installments.

- The debtor sells the goods there to the buyer of the goods.

- Investors receive the final selling price and income.

Sukuk indexed for private infrastructure financing: Istisna ' Sukuk

An exception is a purchase and sale agreement between the seller and the buyer for the production of goods. This method is usually used in the sale of goods that take a lot of time to produce or take time to deliver. According to the situation in the contract, the sale can be paid in cash, in installments or later. [16. 150]

Istisna sukuk-certificates of equal value issued in order to ensure the necessary funds for the production of products belonging to the certificate holder. While the proceeds from membership are the cost of the product, the issuers of the certificates are the manufacturers (seller/supplier) and the members are the buyers of the planned product. The buyers of the certificate own the product and are entitled to the sale price of the product sold, except for the sale price of the certificate or in parallel. Istisna sukuk is useful for financing large infrastructure projects. Istisna is suitable for financial intermediation because it allows the contractor in Istisna to conclude a parallel exception agreement with the subcontractor. For this reason, a financial institution can carry out a construction operation for profit and transfer the construction operation to a specialized firm with a subcontractor agreement [15. 22]. On the other hand, when considering graph 1, it is seen that the types of sukuk most commonly used in Islamic Capital Markets, International and domestic markets are the same as the aforementioned types of sukuk.

OVERVIEW OF SUKUK MARKETS IN THE WORLD AND TURKEY.

The Gulf of Malaysia region, which ranks first in the world sukuk market, is one of the main places for the issue of sukuk; the first sukuk was issued in Malaysia in 1983 [14. 79]. On the other hand, looking at the continuation of sukuk applications, in 2001 the Malaysian government carried out the production of sukuk on a large scale. Initially exported at US 5 500 million, 51% of Malaysian sukuk was sold in the Gulf countries, 30% in Asia, 15% in Europe and 4% in the United States [9. 98]. The implemented structure is the Federal Land Authority of Malaysia, which is a government agency that ensures the transfer of land under its ownership by an established SPV (Public Asset Company) and the rental income received from there through the sale to the Malaysian treasury. SPV issued sukuk as income to the individuals sold. It was built in the building. The capital market Council of Malaysia has linked the issuance of sukuk to strict regulations. Unlike other bond issues, it brought additional obligations. For example, to issue sukuk in Malaysia, the consent of the "Shar-i Soviet commission", consisting of persons recognized and declared by the SC, is required. Thus, the compliance of export-based activities with Islamic principles was recorded. Export-related data and documents and export-related explanations are published in the list. All issues should be evaluated by rating agencies recognized by the SC. In addition, if all Islamic financial instruments are not listed on the Malaysian stock exchanges, they must be subject to a fully automated issuance/tender system implemented by SC and a real-time electronic transfer system of funds and securities.

In fact, the sukuk market has shown growing growth in the world over the past 10 years. According

to the International Islamic Financial Market Data, International Sukuk transactions amount to US 1 100-200 million per month. The issue is still small compared to traditional bonds issued mainly by the government (Bahrain, Malaysia, Qatar and Pakistan), the private sector, international organizations and, to a lesser extent, Islamic banks.

Sukuk world within Islamic financing.

Regarding the issue of sukuk in Turkey, The Capital Market Council (SMB) prepared a communique in 2010. According to the CMB communiqué, sukuk is defined as a rental certificate in Turkey. The communiqué notes that the lease certificate is offered to our capital market as a tool similar to sukuk, which has become a global investment instrument and is also defined as "interest-free bonds", since the withdrawal of funds from capital markets by issuing leasing certificates to private sector companies. In the CMB communiqué, the lease certificate is defined as a tool that allows private sector companies (primary institution) to obtain financing through the use of assets owned or acquired through leasing through an "asset leasing company" (VKS). give-rent-take method. It was noted that a structure called a special purpose organization (trust) VKSH abroad is regulated as a joint-stock company, which is created with a minimum of obligations, since it is not in the legal system of our country. In order to protect the rights of investors with a communique and prevent the abuse of assets accepted by the VKS on behalf of investors or the income from these assets, the APL Charter is mandatory. must meet certain conditions and be approved by the CMB.

The rental certificate issuance system is basically based on a primary institution receiving funds by leasing assets later transferred to the ALC. VKS covers the financing of these assets acquired by it at the first stage with a lease certificate issued by it and makes periodic payments of these certificates with periodic rental income from the original institution. The income received from said assets returned to the original institution at the end of the maturity period is distributed to the holders of the lease certificate in proportion to their shares, and the issued lease certificate is depreciated. this allows them to have rights in accordance with their share in income. In this definition, an asset leasing company (ALC); is a joint-stock company created only by intermediary institutions, banks and resource institutions for the issuance of lease certificates. What does being mean; any movable or immovable property and intangible assets purchased or leased by an asset leasing company. If the original institution; It is a joint-stock company that transfers assets owned or leased to a leasing company (SPK, Communique, 2010). Study of sukuk experience in Turkey Kuwait Türk Katılık Bankası A. The first issue made by Sh on August 17, 2010 was долларды 100 million and the securities were traded at a fixed income rate of 0.5.25% and a maturity date until August 2013. In Turkey, where the population is predominantly Muslim, this first use of the sukuk issue, which is a bond under Islamic rules, attracted great attention and was seen as an indicator of the country's openness and readiness for alternative Islamic financial structures. On the other hand, on September 18,

2012, the Treasury Board authorized a trio of Citigroup, HSBC and Liquty houses, and a cy 1.5 billion Sukuk was put up for sale. As a result of the first tender, 5 requests were received. 58% of sukuk represents the Middle East, 13% Europe, 12% Asia, and 9% sukuk represents the aggregate and retained share of ownership in a tangible asset as it relates to a specific project or specific investment activity. The investor in sukuk does not own the bond issuer's debt obligation, but rather owns a portion of the asset associated with the investment. This means that Sukuk owners, unlike bondholders, receive a portion of the income from the relevant asset. The most common type of sukuk comes in the form of a certificate of trust. These certificates are regulated by Western laws, however, the structure of this type of sukuk is much more complex. The fundraising organization first creates an offshore special purpose vehicle (SPV). The SPV then issues certificates of trust to qualified investors and puts the proceeds from the investment into a financing agreement with the issuing organization. In return, investors receive a portion of the profit associated with the asset.

Sukuk structured as trust certificates only apply if SPV can be established in an offshore jurisdiction that allows such a trust. This is sometimes impossible. If SPV and trust certificates cannot be established, sukuk can be structured as an alternative civil law entity. In this scenario, an asset leasing company will be created in the country of issue, which will profitably purchase the asset and return it to the organization in need of financing.

Production of sukuk on the market of Kazakhstan.

On July 20, 2013, JSC "Development Bank of Kazakhstan" (DBK) "Sukuk" Al-Murabaha " successfully issued Islamic bonds in the amount of 240 million Malaysian riggits at 5.50% per annum and with a maturity of 5 years [4]. The bank reported that 62% was distributed among Malaysian investors, and the remaining 38% in the Kazakhstan market. "Development Bank of Kazakhstan" became the first state in the former Soviet government to issue Islamic precious Kagaz sukuk in accordance with the principles and norms of Sharia. Development prospects of the Islamic Development Bank [1.47-50]. Kazakhstan and the Islamic Development Bank have developed a partnership strategy for 2012-14. The volume of investments covered by target sectors of the economy, such as transport and energy infrastructure, agriculture, science and technology, is more than доллардан 1 billion. For 10 years, the Islamic Development Bank has been ranked highly by 3 main international rating agencies. Zero risk in the projects in which he participated, does not pose any threat to the national and world economy, does not pose any problems [4]. "The program "" successfully "" will be implemented in September this year at the expense of funds raised by the Islamic Development Bank (IDB), ""fund for financial support of Agriculture "" JSC plans." Aktobe, Pavlodar and South Kazakhstan regions were approved as pilot regions for the implementation of the program.

Conclusion

The Islamic financial system is built on the principle of Justice. Just as there is justice in society, in the family, in the service, there must be justice in the financial system. The distribution of both income and expenses by Islamic banks on an equal basis with the entrepreneur is a real manifestation of this Justice. In developed states, only rich people see the fun of both banking and earnings. And in a country that has adopted the Islamic financial system, all this is common to the people. Like other countries of the world, Kazakhstan must adopt the Islamic financial system if it wants to get out of the economic crisis. The Islamic economy will benefit all people with different living standards, effectively solving the problem of unemployment. The baidaly orator has a saying: "first of all, what is bad is bad." Without sharing the risk with the client, the return skyrocketed the interest rate of the funds, and the raft of banks that were easily overwhelmed by excess money disappeared. If the Islamic Development Bank is permanently established in the country and operates regularly, there is great hope for the future of the economy of our state, especially the financial system. In my opinion, I am sure that the financial situation of our country will be better if such a situation is established. Because, firstly, this system is based on purity. It also has a clear goal – to improve the social situation of the population. Today, in our country and even around the world, there is an understanding that "we can live on credit." That is, people are completely accustomed to credit. And Islamic financing is of great importance in the final elimination of this unpromising trend.

The financial market is a part of the loan capital market, where capital is redistributed between lenders and borrowers in the form of the issue and purchase and sale of sukuk securities. The financial market can be considered as a combination of primary and secondary markets. The primary market appears at the time of issue of securities, on which financial funds are mobilized. In the secondary market, these reserves are redistributed several times. The secondary market is divided into exchange and over-the-counter markets. On the exchange market, which are specialized stock exchanges, shares of leading companies are bought and sold, and on the over-the-counter market, securities whose price is not set on the exchange for various reasons. From an institutional point of view, the financial market is credit and financial institutions, through which financial flows flow from owners to borrowers and vice versa. Such inflows take the form of transferring financial funds directly from lenders to borrowers without any financial intermediaries. The incompatibility of interests is eliminated by financial intermediaries, which include financial institutions: commercial banks, credit unions, stock exchanges, financial companies, pension and insurance funds, investment banks, construction societies, etc. Financial intermediaries, if necessary, combine the funds of several lenders to meet the significant needs of borrowers and take on a potential risk (risk), thus playing an important role in the stabilization of KN.

It has shown that all potential issuers can follow the leadership of securities and effectively use the

sukuk platform to expand the investor base, improve liquidity and access Islamic financial products in new markets. It contributes to the development of the Islamic finance industry in Kazakhstan and the region, as well as the positioning of sukuk as an International Center for Islamic finance.

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